

ADVERSE IMPACT ON THE ECONOMY OF INDIAN TOURISM INDUSTRY DUE TO COVID -19 PANDEMIC

Himanshu Arya

Head of Department, Tour & Hospitality Department
Dr. MPS Group of Institutions, Agra, India

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ABSTRACT

The world economy has been brought to a complete stand still due to the Covid-19 pandemic. Every citizen, every employee of all the cadre suffered financially as well as socially also due to sudden closure of every industry and every business due to this pandemic. The tourism & aviation is among the few that have been suffered a lot due to adverse effect of this pandemic. The purpose of present study aims to analyze the adverse effect on the economy of tourism industry with its different sectors survival ratio affected due to this pandemic. In present study the future of post Covid scenario and method adopted by the different tour and travel agencies so that future strategies can be planned to sustain the economy in more sustainable and safe manner.

Key words: Covid 19, adverse effect, economy, lock-down

INTRODUCTION

Due to imposition of strict lock-down on travel around the world resultant into frozen of entire tourism sector. Several countries like U.K., USA, China, Russia, Japan, France etc. imposes restrictions on movement of people which directly hit the entire economical sectors not only this the physiological, sociological & Psychological well being of a person with specific reference to tour & travel industry. This was analyzed by (Aliperti et al, 2019)., Cro,S., & Martins, A.M. (2017)., Page, S., Song, H. & Wu, DC (2012)., Ranjith, P., & Varma (2020) Qiu, PL & Song. (2020) Ritchie, B.W., & Jiangy (2019) Jaipuria, S., Parida, R., & Ray, P. (2020)., Seadra, C., Reis, P., & Abrantes, J.L. (2020). On 25th March 2020 India Government imposes complete lock down and movement from one state to other state was also banned which resultant into frozen of entire tourism industry. Since long time tourism industry has been a primary source of revenue & employment generating unit of many countries. Due to lock-down in March 2020 the tourist arrival in India decline up to 66.4% as compared to 2019. It has been reported that due to job

losses in India the loss of revenue reaches to the extent of approximate USD 17 billion. (Allel, F., & Carletti, (E 2010)., Bagliano, F. C., & Morana, C. (2012)., Mandel, A., Veetil, B. (2020)., Mial, A., & Sufi, A. (2010). There are several factors which were responsible for a sharp fall of the economy of entire tourism industry such as complete ban on movement, job losses, closure of production unit, however, due to well planning of Indian Government for control of spread of Covid-19 save the economy from sharp fall.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

In any industry or sector various sub sectors are involves which are closely related to each other and interdependence is required to achieve the smooth functioning and coordination of several sectors. The bonding of all the elite sector, their synchronization and harmony in working is utmost required in any industry. The same is true with the tourism sector. The Indian tourism sector has been considered as highly insensible and largely influence from the attitude and choice of a tourist. Every tourist wants to admire adventures and feel different experiences rather than focusing on a particular product. Several factors including geographic, psychographic and demographic determines the characteristics of various destination and tourist places. (Nathan, N. 2020) The relationships of any country with other country play a predominant role in the sustenance and the survival of a destination's tourism industry.

The relationship depends on the policies of the government and regulatory bodies, their economic and fiscal policy etc. The entire tourism industry of world including India came to a complete stand-still due to strict restrictions on the visitor and not allows anyone to visit any country or state at that time. Due to restrictions on movement of the countrymen generated great crises in all fronts of economy even then stock market has also been crashed. In early time the world tourism was adversely affected due to many events such as terrorist attack 9/11, several epidemics like SARS, CoV-2, Ebola, Swine Flu etc. The same devastating effect of COVID-19 observed. As per government policies all the flights, air transport, railways become sudden shut down which created major crises resulted in challenging task of survival for tourism sector. (The Hindu, 2020 A.)

COMPARATIVE EMPLOYMENT STATUS FROM 2018 TO 2021.

****Source: Center for Monitoring Survey.**

Due to sudden lock down the entire tourism sector was adversely affected, but it was more severe in the countries which are having religious and pilgrimage tourism sites, out of which India was one of them. Majority of the tourist cancelled their journey and booking from the travel agencies causes a great loss to the market. Due to complete lock down the back bone of Indian economy become injured and reached to a dangerous point.

Comparison from 2018 to 2021 is given below as graphical representation:

India Unemployment Rate From 2018 To 2021

****Source: Centre For Monitoring Survey.**

THE DYNAMIC ADVERSE FACTORS OF COVID 19 ON INDIA TOURISM BUSINESS:

In India summer is the peak season for tourist destinations and other places, in Rajasthan and the hills and season start from April to July. During its peak time the infection of COVID-19 cripes with a faster speed which resulted in huge loss of life and wealth. The summer destination observed more than 40% fall in tourist arrival was observed.

Related	Last	Previous	Unit	Reference
	392930.00	342308.00		Apr 2022
Tourism Revenues	58330.00	182810.00	INR Million	Mar 2020

Due to COVID-19 destruction progresses ultimately resulted adversely affected nation employment.

POST LOCKDOWN TOURISM IN INDIA:

Slowly and gradually the influence of Covid-19 is going to be diluted and all short of restrictions from the boundaries has been uplifted. So, now tourism industry can revive up to their pre- lock down period. In November 2021 the things are to be going to be normal although many companies are still offering work from home due to some other reasons. Now a day's home stays in tourist destinations are becoming more popular as tourist get all sorts of safety and security majors at the destinations. Every hotel, guest houses and home stays are ensuring standards of safety and securities in all the sectors of tourism industry. The aviation business is also executing safety measures and infrastructural development and automation are advancing day by day. Most of the functions are conducting with automatic, smart security appliances.

CONCLUSION

This review article has examined the greater impact which was developed by the viral infection resultant into a major damage to the economy of the world including India. Now the things are changing and improving with a cheerful spirit. The vaccination has been popular in whole world and peoples are well aware with the benefits of it and also taking due precautions for all the other related aspects. Now hopefully it is estimated that tourism sector will soon get its back glory with sumptuous financial inputs. By use of the strategic implementation of the desired policies and attention towards the market trends along with the enormous use of artificial intelligence the tourism sector can flourish again.

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